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Reconstruction of new media artworks: a theoretical model and two pilot studies

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Abstract

The technological aspect of new media art presents a complex issue for museums or artists wishing to preserve new media artworks for an extended period of time. Additionally, new media art typically exists at a fragile threshold of potentiality: through imagination and the implementation of new technical solutions, it reflects societal changes by shaping emerging communication models. This paper addresses various challenges in reconstructing and preserving new media artworks and describes several theoretical and practical approaches successfully implemented in Slovenia. Our theoretical framework highlights three parameters that define a new media object: **1)** the interfaces-database relation, **2)** single-user game-like interaction vs. digital community platform, and **3)** machine-based creativity. These parameters can be employed to assess whether and how the original and reconstructed projects retain their fundamental characteristics, and if these changes align with the repercussions of technological mediation in society as well. The paper presents two pilot studies on the

reconstruction of new media artworks that were nonfunctional in 2022: from 2000, *Nation – Culture* by Vuk Ćosić, and from 2005, *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club* by Srečo Dragan.

Keywords

born-digital cultural heritage; artwork reconstruction; Slovenian new media art; Vuk Ćosić; Srečo Dragan

Reconstrucción de obras de arte de los nuevos medios: un modelo teórico y dos estudios piloto

Resumen

*El aspecto tecnológico de arte de los nuevos medios presenta un problema complejo para los museos o artistas que desean conservar las obras de arte de dicha tipología durante un período prolongado. Además, el arte de los nuevos medios normalmente existe en un frágil umbral de potencialidad: a través de la imaginación y la implementación de nuevas soluciones técnicas, refleja los cambios sociales al dar forma a los modelos de comunicación emergentes. Este documento aborda varios desafíos en la reconstrucción y conservación de obras de arte de los nuevos medios y describe varios enfoques teóricos y prácticos implementados con éxito en Eslovenia. Nuestro marco teórico destaca tres parámetros que definen el arte de los nuevos medios: 1) la relación interfaz-base de datos, 2) la interacción similar a un juego de un solo usuario frente a la de plataforma de comunidad digital y 3) la creatividad basada en máquinas. Estos parámetros pueden emplearse para evaluar si los proyectos originales y reconstruidos conservan sus características fundamentales y cómo, y si estos cambios se alinean también con las repercusiones de la mediación tecnológica en la sociedad. El artículo presenta dos estudios piloto sobre la reconstrucción de obras de arte de los nuevos medios que no fueron funcionales en 2022: del 2000, *Nation – Culture* de Vuk Ćosić, y del 2005, *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club* de Srečo Dragan.*

Palabras clave

herencia cultural nacida digital; reconstrucción de obras de arte; arte esloveno de los nuevos medios; Vuk Ćosić; Srečo Dragan

Introduction: tackling the preservation of new media art in Slovenia

In Slovenia, there are few initiatives that address the preservation and restoration of new media cultural heritage. Since 2004, the Computer History Museum, a private initiative, has focused on preserving and restoring old computers and software. In addition, the manuscript department of the National and University Library holds some software works. A video archive called DIVA Station (Digital Video Archive) contains, in addition to video art, some video documentation of media artworks (SCCA-Ljubljana n.d.). Primarily, the maintenance of archives and the preservation of new media artworks falls on the shoulders of the artists themselves. Jaka Železnikar, an author of early net.art projects, has reconstructed his own works several times by updating them. However, such a model is not sustainable (Polónyi, 2023; 2024). To address the multifaceted problems surrounding the longevity of new media art, net artist Igor Štromajer decided to delete his early works as his “last net art project” (*Expunction*, 2011).

In the framework of the *Sustainable Digital Preservation of the Slovenian New Media Art* research project (2021-2024), researchers from various fields addressed important issues related to the preservation of born-digital cultural heritage. Our interdisciplinary approach encompassed art historical and media theoretical methodologies, comparative literature, informatics, and perspectives from legal scholarship. In this paper, we will present our two pilot reconstructions of new media artworks. This paper focuses on the preservation of new media artworks in a narrow sense, excluding video, time-based media, or variable media, and examines the dilemmas of developing a preservation strategy for a major public museum within the Slovenian context. It does not provide an overview of the field of new media art preservation.¹ It can be observed that the musealization and preservation processes (e.g. conservation and restoration) always transform their objects. This is particularly evident in projects highly dependent on data environments.

As conceived, the project focused on theoretical aspects of new media art preservation, however, by the start of the funding a new im-

1. In our project we e.g. explored the use of large language models, such as ChatGPT, as art preservation tools (Solina 2023).

portant partner joined the project, the Museum of Modern Art (Moderna galerija), the Slovenian national cultural institution dedicated to modern and contemporary art. The two new media art projects that we chose for our pilot studies were presented at the Museum of Contemporary Art Metelkova. The exhibition of *Nation – Culture* by Vuk Ćosić (*Nacija – Kultura*, 13 Oct. 2022 - 8 Feb. 2023) was based on the artist's project from 2000,² whereas the exhibition of the techno-performance *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club* by Srečo Dragan (Matrica koincidenca zmenkarski klub, 19 Jan. 2023) reconstructed Dragan's project from 2005 (cf. Moderna galerija, 2023).

Although this museum's mission is to collect and preserve modern visual and contemporary art in the broadest sense, and no other state-founded institution exists to take care of media art and born-digital art, the project has faced opposition from within the museum and from some art experts; moreover, this attitude had wider political roots. Consider the following statement:

“uncritical favoring of new media and digital content at the expense of ‘living’ culture, [...] has caused the erosion or even the disintegration and abolition of public space, which is a place of democratic confrontations, critical thinking and civil society.” (Gibanje Svoboda 2022, 26)

In the quote from the governing political party's programme for arts and culture, the preference for the digital ultimately corresponds with a significant erosion of critical thinking. Technophobia surrounding new media art – and the digital-humanities paradigm shift in general – extends to certain commentaries regarding art history and museology in Slovenia. In another instance, a scholar expresses her views on the digitization of museum objects as having “failed.”

“[T]he reason for the alleged, temporary or permanent ‘failure’ of the realization of the virtual museum must be sought in the nature of museum objects as physical entities, and the consequent question, which aspects of museum objects can in fact be digitized at all” (Mahnič 2023, 73).

The digital preservation and manipulation of museum objects is thus dismissed as questionable. As cultural heritage professionals are likely to concur, the museum object is a more or less autonomous and self-sufficient physical entity, serving as a substantial source of knowledge. However, approaches to traditional preservation are clearly ill-suited for the preservation of born-digital objects. Although these are, of course, also “physical,” the legibility of such new media art materiality necessitates new-media literacy and an appropriate infrastructure.

The cultural-heritage domain is a contested and situated field that seeks to save from oblivion culturally significant entities and related processes. The open question remains: what is significant among new media art objects, and what could be left to be forgotten? The value of new media art becomes an important and disputed issue. In addressing the problem of preserving Slovenian born-digital heritage within the art domain, we aimed to focus on real opportunities and constraints.

Grounded in a commitment to the new media artists' perspective on preservation, the project leaders selected examples of Slovenian new media art based on the levels of access we had to their original creators, as well as the works that demonstrate the highest levels of accomplishment. It is also notable that these artists view the restoration of older works as a creative reinvention or reconstruction of the original idea for contemporary use. This approach diverges from the rebuilding of the works in their original form. It clearly identifies all the changes that occurred during the work's reconstruction and the encoding of meaning from the original piece. This reconstruction, along with the reinterpretation by the author, offers the possibility of reflecting on the stability of artefacts, technologies and society.

Slovenian new media art is internationally recognized and acknowledged (e.g. Edward Zajec, Dragan Živadinov, Marko Peljhan, Maja Smrekar). The works of many authors from Slovenia have been presented and awarded at major international new media art festivals. The tradition of new media festivals in Slovenia (in Maribor since 1995, in Nova Gorica and Trbovlje), along with writings by theorists such as Janez Strehovec, demonstrate the significant contributions made in the new media domain during the periods of Yugoslavia and Slovenia.

The two authors selected for the preservation pilot studies are among these key protagonists. Vuk Ćosić is best known for his net art work with the early World Wide Web. His work features prominently in *The Language of New Media* by Lev Manovich (2001), as well as extensively in the monograph *Internet Art* by Rachael Greene (2004; cf. Paul 2003; Rush 2005). In 2001, Ćosić himself reviewed the history of net art internationally (Ćosić 2001). Srečo Dragan, along with Nuša Dragan, was a video pioneer in Yugoslavia (Bovcon, 2008; 2009). Their work was presented as part of the key early festivals of computer and media art in Yugoslavia (Studentski kulturni centar n.d.; Rosen 2011). Their joint early work in video until 1988 and Srečo Dragan's solo work in computer art since then were showcased in two major retrospective exhibitions at the Museum of Modern Art in Ljubljana in 2000 and in 2016-2017.

The two new media artworks selected for our pilot projects, *Nation – Culture* and *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club*, are particularly challenging to preserve since their constituent parts have disappeared or changed dramatically with technological advancements and transformations. However, upon later analysing the reconstructions, we obtained valuable insights that led to a theoretical model for approaching the reconstruction of new media artworks, as we will demonstrate here. In conclusion, we argue that both projects and their reconstructions offer a critical reflection on contemporary digital information and communication technologies by scrutinizing the existing technical solutions and their contextual applications.

2. Curated by Aleš Vaupotič (cf. Moderna galerija 2022).

1. Theoretical framework: three parameters for describing and analysing new media artworks

We contend that the genealogy of new media art could support preservation efforts (cf. Bovcon 2024; Vaupotič 2024). As it is impossible to fully address the issue of genres of new media art in this text, we shall, for our purposes, use the concept of genre as a perspective that arises from groupings of works that are interrelated based on mutual references, i.e. that belong to a single tradition.³ Genres are constructed less synthetically than theoretical categories. They gather empirical insights and craft-oriented guidelines that govern artistic production in practice. They emerge, transform, and fade away. Clarity regarding the genre-related aspects of a given artwork highlights the artwork's main constituent parts or aspects. This is particularly relevant in the case of new media art since the material features presented to viewers-users can be almost anything: from line drawings to screen-based computer games, brain-computer interfaces, or mapping of data using various media to automatic text generators, etc.

The first parameter relevant for defining new media art genres is articulated in Lev Manovich's definition of a new media object as a multimedia database with multiple interfaces (2001). According to Manovich, a single interface to a database constitutes a traditional art object, for example, a painting. Manovich's reflection is thus aligned with the double bind of concrete art projects; namely, the need to construct or find a database or some source material that audiences are (interested in) communicating with, and, on the other hand, a malleable interface that mediates the often two-way exchange between an addressee and the art project as a sender. In this respect, new media art projects can be positioned on a continuum between algorithmic generators (e.g. the dynamic light objects by Vladimir Bonačić, such as *DIN. PR18* from 1969) (Compart n.d.), which foreground the algorithms behind the presentation of highly abstracted source content, and, on the other end of the spectrum, projects that emphasize the efforts involved in building an archive (e.g. George Legrady's *Pockets Full of Memories* from 2000; Fondation Daniel Langlois 2000).

The second feature to consider when examining the genre of new media art is the shift from single-user cybertext, such as hypertext fiction, to multi-user environments, like collaborative projects on platforms such as Wikipedia (Vaupoti 2012). This differentiation was introduced by Espen Aarseth (1997), who built on the tradition of reader-response criticism and complemented it with a theory of (literary) cybertext that views text not as a stable and fixed medium for reader consumption, but as a textual machine that a reader-user manipulates in order to configure and interact with the words, functioning like an interface that is also read. This approach allows for an in-depth analysis

of the user's engagement with the text and the complex process of negotiating communication among various participants, including programmers and storytellers (Elstermann 2023). The reading experience must change radically because the new media artwork, as a textual machine, fuses algorithms (used in games or Turing machines) with human interpretation. In a single-user project, an individual encounters rule-based feedback from a selection of elements within an archive. Concurrently, she engages in gameplay while reading or watching a narrative that is then interpreted in a particular way. The rules govern access, requiring the user to solve tasks akin to riddles.⁴ Conversely, in the second type of cybertext, or multi-user cybertext, digital platforms where users contribute and communicate with one another demand a completely new social agreement. Such cybertexts evolve alongside active groups of users with hierarchically diverse roles, for example, as (art-centred) digital communities. In this model, the measure of success is the levels of social cohesion and the sustainability of ongoing communication, while the game-like rules themselves are no longer the primary focus. From the cybertextual perspective, the author (or preservationist) faces a binary choice: either view the new media art project as a blend of game-playing and the reading of multimedia texts, or perceive it as a new and sustainable society of users based on a novel digital communication platform (Vaupoti 2010, 324-327).

The third aspect regarding the determination of genre concerns whether a machine and its algorithms can generate truly meaningful content that can then be interpreted through the artwork's reception. Are there any emergent features arising from the mechanical processes within the machines that create non-human-based meaningful content? This question has already been addressed by Aarseth, according to whom it could be construed as a zero-user cybertext. In this scenario, there is no need for transformative active interaction with the textual interface; the meaningful text-stream is produced automatically, as if by an intelligent being.

Aside from the current dilemmas concerning (multimodal) large language models and other generative artificial intelligence techniques, it is important to recognize a relatively straightforward case from early Google. In this example, the PageRank algorithm bibliometrically sorts quality content from the masses of online spam (Brin & Page 1998; Battelle 2006). The speed of data transfer and processing enables previously impossible textual artefacts. In *The Ethics of Artificial Intelligence* (2023), Luciano Floridi highlights that there is no human-like consciousness in machines, at least not within the foreseeable future. What is novel for Floridi and striking is that, in the separation of conscious thinking and agency, artificial intelligence proves to be a vast resource of agency that needs to be viewed as both an opportunity and a challenge (p. 24).

3. Cf. Bolter & Grusin 2000; Rettberg 2019; Elstermann 2023; Reed 2023; and the Bakhtinian theory of discourse.

4. Apart from art, this phenomenon is increasingly present in administrative, healthcare and other services for citizens that are being digitized globally: the users have to obey the rules of the interfaces to gain access.

To summarize, new media artworks can be described along three parameters: **1)** the continuum of database and interfaces; **2)** the dichotomy between single-user cybertext (game-playing and readerly experience) and multi-user discourse (a digital community); and **3)** the criterion of machine-based meaning production that cannot be reduced to a mere collage of human records. These parameters can serve as a framework to identify items and artwork components to be archived in a preservation project tailored to new media art. The two pilot projects will be described and analysed according to these three parameters in their original and reconstructed forms.

2.1. Pilot study: *Nation – Culture* by Vuk Ćosić

Apart from being a world-renowned and iconic figure in the realm of Internet art, Vuk Ćosić was selected as a case study for this project due to a specific artwork of his and its significance for the theory of new media art. *Nation – Culture* represents an early and compelling case for arguing that the textual output is generated automatically by the machine itself, with only the ability to move and display data being utilised elsewhere for other purposes, and that such a text, in a weird way, makes some sense to people. Linguistically raw inputs from Slovenian-speaking Web users from 2000 can be regarded as a pure sample of the Slovenian language and thus indicative of the so-called national spirit in a Hegelian sense, whether this formulation is intended ironically or not. However, this is not a conceptual-art project in the sense that the realization of the apparatus and the presentation of the webstream would be rendered redundant or unnecessary; on the contrary, the software-and-network hybrid shifts cultural content and thereby imparts a new, previously inaccessible meaning. Considering the three parameters, *Nation – Culture* constitutes an argument in favour of the validity of automatised artistic-content creation. It is important to note that it is not a remix; rather, it is a phenomenon arising from the existence of new information streams that can now be observed. This, of course, is not, by any means, a secret anymore as it may have been perceived in 2000, given the ubiquity of micrometering and personalization services today. However, in this instance, the outcome is not an advertising campaign but a genuine artwork. Furthermore, it is worth noting that this project is not fully explained by categorizing it as playful; instead, it represents a critical engagement with the Internet and the World Wide Web from within net art practices. Additionally, the non-human production of meaning extends beyond net art.

Vuk Ćosić showcased his *Nation – Culture* for the first time in 2000 for a commemorative exhibition on the Slovene national poet France Prešeren, a figure from the Romantic period (Vaupotič 2013). At that time, Ćosić employed an ingenious (and arguably controversial) solution to give an animated text-stream in the form of a sonnet (projected in a museum) some cognizable meaning. He used a search stream of all the

real-time queries on the Slovene Yahoo-type web portal Mat'Kurja. The hidden murmur of Slovenians' voices on web 1.0 was thus made visible and exposed without any restriction or manipulation. Consequently, the "nation" emerges as more or (often) less "cultured", i.e. well behaved. According to the author, the dash in the title may therefore be interpreted as "minus".

For the 2022 reconstruction, the author aimed to preserve the experimental-disruptive-transgressive element. He emphasised the project's relevance for audiences in 2022, having personally encountered hate speech on Twitter. Consequently, he pushed the technological solution to the new limits of the state of the art. This clearly does not represent non-critical technophilia on his part, but rather reflects the understanding that, at any point, technological solutions will shape our world. GPT-2 was employed to train a language model on Slovene tweets, first to learn the language, and was subsequently fine-tuned on Slovene poetry before generating sonnets.⁵ Each sonnet begins with a post on Twitter by a select group of Slovene politicians and copywriters/journalists, which also serves as a prompt for writing-rendering the rest of the sonnet.

Figure 1. Vuk Ćosić: *Nation – Culture*, 2000

Source: image courtesy of Vuk Ćosić

Concerning the question of whether a machine and its algorithms can generate actual artistic content that can then be interpreted at the moment of the artwork's reception, we observe that in Vuk Ćosić's project from 2000, a machine somehow extracted or produced meaningful text without any author-like intention or pre-prepared meanings.

5. Programmed by Marko Plahuta (Plahuta 2023, 18 min. 9 sec.). This project was realized before the GPT-3-based ChatGPT international launch.

Slovenians had been using the web portal technology in question, and, contrary to everyday communication, which is ephemeral, the digitized messages could be – and were – collected by the search engine. Meaningfulness was, therefore, based on the ability to transfer data rather than on creativity on the part of the machine. Nevertheless, the project informed the viewer about the Slovenian “spirit,” or national imaginary, which, for instance, the then-contemporary recombinational apparatuses for poetry had failed to do, since, in those cases, either the understanding of the rules takes over (i.e. the single-user cybertext option), or the project’s emphasis shifts to the conceptual level (e.g. Hans Magnus Enzensberger, Fluxus, Oulipo,...). The *ChatGPT* online service later satisfied the criterion of creating something that a human can perceive as meaningful. In the visual domain, a similar effect is achieved when using, for example, Stable Diffusion models, where a textual prompt results in an original, i.e. a new, image.

Figure 2. Vuk Ćosić: *Nation – Culture*, 2022. Sonnet-shaped responses to the tweets by the prime minister – the tweet is the prompt and also the beginning of the sonnet (in italics)
Source: Image courtesy of MG+MSUM

The reception of the reconstructed project and the exhibition in Ljubljana was significant for several reasons. It critically addressed hate speech online, which was actively provoked to a considerable extent by right-wing political parties and the media in Slovenia, although, of course, not exclusively. In parallel, the reconstruction, or reactualization, of the work, along with the ensuing exhibition, sparked public discussion on the use of artificial intelligence for writing texts and even literature. Several books of sonnets were published, which were, of course, written by the custom GPT-2 model, and a crown of crowns of crowns of sonnets has been planned (the first “corona of coronas” was already published as a printed book; Ćosić, 2022).⁶ Finally, the combination of both aspects foregrounded the pressing issue of digital and new media literacy in public discourse and everyday use, which was one of the key goals of our research project.

6. Cf. the links on the exhibition web page (Moderna galerija 2022).

7. Dinkla, 1996. The complex relationship between apparatus theory in cinema discourse, media archaeology and art history is pointed to by Eszter Polónyi (2016).

2.2. Pilot study: Matrix Coincidence Dating Club by Srečo Dragan

Srečo Dragan’s work is rooted in early explorations of the video medium, particularly as a closed-circuit video installation. His works, alongside Nuša Dragan, from the late 1960s investigated how video could be incorporated into happenings to enhance participants’ self-awareness and their ability to articulate their environment and circumstances. Thus, through his work, it became evident that interpersonal relationships between individuals could also be examined and deepened through a visual-art medium. Interaction with the video screen in a closed-loop installation could be seen as a bridge from traditional arts to an understanding of the social value of new media and computer art.⁷ This chosen project was the most intricate among Dragan’s works, as it featured a kind of matchmaking game involving both the gaze of the machine and interpersonal relationships that extended beyond the boundaries of the artwork. The practical efficiency of the digital processing of data via computer vision in the work was balanced by the need to reimagine interpersonal relationship-building for the digital era.

Srečo Dragan presented his *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club* as an exhibition in Ljubljana, first held in 2005. It consisted of three main elements. Initially, the user had to formally agree to participate by signing a consent form and submitting her mobile phone number. Then, she stepped onto a platform that measures pressure as a force vector, with music from an internet radio station encouraging the person to dance. This dance constituted the “matrix” that is learned and culturally imprinted on individuals. It was non-immanent and accessible to rational reflection and control. This stage was not recorded; however, it was visible to other visitors in the gallery, as the space of interaction was not hidden. The matrix-phase served as a sort of ritual purification before the second and key stage of gait recognition *via* computer vision. The participant walked on a treadmill; her portrait was taken, and her movements were recorded and analysed. The “coincidence” emphasised similarities in the way we walk, which represents a layer of individuality that one cannot control or fake and that is not susceptible to cultural stereotypes or biases related to gender and social roles, according to Dragan. The computer algorithms recognize the individual’s walking patterns to propose non-discriminatory matches between participants. The portraits of the resulting pairs of visitors were displayed in the gallery, forming an archival room. In the third segment, the two matched participants received a text message on their personal mobile phones to meet at a specified time and location, namely, a café (their mobile phone numbers were not disclosed). The participants could then decide whether to meet or not. Additionally, a webcam connection was established between the gallery space and the café.

Figure 3. Srečo Dragan: *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club*, 2005. The dance-visualization, i.e. the “matrix” on the left, and gait recognition measurements, the “coincidence” on the right
Source: image courtesy of Srečo Dragan

From the perspective of new media art preservation, the issue of gait recognition was the most sensitive aspect of this project. Between 2005 and 2007, software from a PhD research project was employed to pair users. However, in 2022, the artist decided to utilize newer artificial intelligence algorithms to reconstruct this core element of the project. Two observations can be made; namely, that gait recognition was implemented without consideration of various technical solutions. Nevertheless, it must also be acknowledged that research in computer vision has enabled the artist to envision how the world makes sense through interactions between people, other beings, and environments. The development of gait analysis can lead in numerous directions, either towards greater societal control or towards establishing connections and creating new possibilities (Dragan 2007).

Dragan collaborated with the Computer Vision Laboratory at the Faculty of Computer and Information Science of the University of Ljubljana on several of his projects, including the 2005 and 2022 versions of our case study project (Solina et al. 2014). What was once a PhD research project in gait recognition in 2005 was, by 2022, easily accomplished as a bachelor’s degree thesis, yielding better results in terms of actual matching by similarity. This indicated that the motivation for the technical solution within the project had shifted. In 2022, since we aimed to maintain the setup from the original installation, the decision was made to use skeleton analysis, a treadmill, and a 90° camera angle on the individual on the treadmill. A database of videos featuring participants walking on the treadmill was subsequently recorded and utilized for training the neural network to identify similar gaits. In the visualisation, images of calculated skeletons were overlaid onto recorded videos of the participants and displayed in pairs, with lines connecting their moving joints, as was already done in the visualization from 2005.

For the reconstruction, we consulted the artist and the brief yet thorough catalogue of the original work (Dragan 2006). This includes photographs from the 2005 exhibition and the conceptual diagrams that outline each laboratory in the gallery. The researchers involved in the reconstruction were familiar with the original installation of the project, which occurred in 2005. However, the students who worked on

the gait analysis had not experienced it and found it difficult to grasp the succinct description in the catalogue. To clarify and preserve the project, we created a digital animation that illustrated the interactions and the precise setup in the gallery.

Figure 4. Srečo Dragan: *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club*, 2022. The 3-D models of the installation set-up, a digital animation

Source: image courtesy of Miha Marinko and Narvika Bovcon

The first room of the project included a laboratory for bio-mechanical measurements, which presented a different challenge. Specifically, the pressure board used in the original set-up in 2005 was borrowed from the Jožef Stefan Institute. Although it had served at that time for research purposes to measure movement, by 2022, it was no longer available. We decided to replace the pressure board with Nintendo’s Wii Balance Board, a popular commercial solution released in 2007. However, the Wii Balance Board was also a discontinued product, which again illustrates the inevitable and rapid obsolescence of new technical gadgets. Nevertheless, we employed it to significantly reduce the cost of custom construction for a pressure board. We utilized the Processing platform to create the desired real-time visualization of the data from the Wii sensors.

For the mobile communication laboratory, we used text messages (SMS), as in 2005. We did not switch to other messaging or social media platforms that are now ubiquitous on smartphones to avoid introducing unnecessary layers of new meanings that the project does not require. The webcam streaming that originally connected the café with the gallery was omitted in the reconstructed version due to privacy concerns and new associations with pervasive teleconferencing, particularly in light of the recent period of epidemic isolation.

Finally, we created a version suitable for school visits to the gallery. Each school group constitutes an isolated run of applications; the children’s portraits and gait measurements are not added to the database, their mobile phone numbers are not required, and no messages for meetings are sent. The school version analyzes only the gait, after which children with similar gaits are displayed on a video screen in the gallery, and all data is subsequently deleted. This aspect was not considered in the original project, as there seemed to be less concern

and awareness regarding privacy issues at that time. Additionally, the original installation had been set up for a short period in a gallery aimed at adult audiences.

What one notices by comparing the creation of Dragan's new works with the preservation of the older ones is that the dialogue between the art domain and research in computer vision and information systems has shifted towards preserving the artistic concept as it was realized in the original version of the project.⁸ As opposed to developing new engineering and scientific insights in the field of informatics and integrating these into the art domain, the reconstruction was primarily used to assess the applications of widely accessible computer vision tools. As an artist, Srečo Dragan has previously addressed the complex issue of later presentations of older works in his retrospective exhibitions. He has explicitly and consciously transformed his works into their own documentation (e.g. as conceptual boards) and linked to them the essential contextual information of their first production, which has helped preserve the meaning over time (Bovcon 2021). Heritage preservation efforts have always faced such a dilemma because the objects in museums are separated from their contexts. Our approach proposes to preserve the key elements that facilitate the experience of the core idea of the work. The author's retrospective shows can, of course, creatively go even further.

Since one of the project partners was also a national museum hosting the national collection of media art, we developed guidelines and protocols to support and document the transfer of works to the museum collections. This particularly concerned those works that, as a rule, were problematic for their authors and producers to maintain in a functional state, even for relatively short periods. In both cases, the small exhibition was combined with the acquisition of the proposed and realized work to provide support for the artists. This proved to work very well, especially considering the limited financial support for new media art in Slovenia. However, the reluctance of the museum staff and the Slovenian Ministry of Culture (after the 2022 elections) to actively engage in the preservation of the born-digital art heritage resulted in the museum's inability to implement the proposed procedures. This also prevented the completion of the analysis of the reception of the reconstructed works in the museum as intended.

2.3. The three parameters in the original and reconstructed projects

In this subsection, we will describe the two projects and their pilot reconstructions using the three genre-related parameters derived from new media theory. These three parameters serve as a theoretical model for comparing the original with reconstructed new media artworks, allowing us to observe the changes, both physical, i.e. technical, and conceptual, i.e. in relation to the works' interpretation.

Nation – Culture (2000, 2022)

Database: in the 2000 version, the database contained online queries and lacked metadata about the users. In 2022, the text was sourced from a custom GPT-2 foundational language model trained on Slovene tweets and news titles, with fine-tuning using Slovenian poetry. **Interfaces:** the sonnet-shaped text, custom font, and text animation were preserved in 2022 and extended to three sonnet generators: **1)** thematic clustering of themes sourced from the news and presented as an animation (as in 2000), **2)** GPT-2 based prints (also printed books of sonnets), and **3)** a live Twitter bot (also printed out and added daily to the exhibition).

No interaction: in 2000, a projected text-flow of real-time data from the Mat'Kurja server; the output is an artefact of the machine. Possibly, though very improbably, a single-user interactive reading (for instance, a misuse of the portal by someone aware of the project). In 2022, the bot "responded" only to tweets by the Slovene prime minister and posted them as replies (and soon got blocked).

Machine creativity: in 2000, the telepresence of voices from different locations – knowledge specific to, or facilitated by, the machine. In 2022, GPT-2 and the news feed classifier (GRU with attention).

Matrix Coincidence Dating Club (2005, 2022)

Database: gait sampling, personal information (photo, telephone number). **Interfaces:** dance and gait visualization, the set-up of the installation as three laboratories, the SMS communication and the meeting in a café.

Single-user interaction: dance visualization and gait analysis both function as single-user interfaces with rule-based interaction. **The community** (i.e. matchmaking) is initiated by the project, but, as such, is outside its scope and is not preserved or maintained.

No machine creativity: the project relies on creating a more open society of individuals, with artificial intelligence in gait recognition serving merely as a means to an end.

The outline above considers the two pilot studies using the three genre-related aspects. We can see that Srečo Dragan's project preserves many of the original features, even though the core element, the method and algorithm for comparing people based on how they walk, was replaced. In Vuk Ćosić's project, the reliance on the Yahoo-type portal presented a significantly larger challenge, as today's World Wide Web and the Internet consist of various types of hubs. The essential aspect, the self-disclosure of the Slovenian national spirit as framed by the new ICTs, was maintained. However, it was also somewhat overshadowed by the evolved climate of the Internet over the past 22 years, as hate speech proliferates through so-called walled gardens of social media and their echo-chamber effects. The fundamental aspects of the project from 2000 (visual and conceptual, including the custom typeface based on the one used in the first publications of Prešeren's

8. Dragan's reconstruction was more closely affiliated with our research project than Ćosić's, also the original production was realized with our collaborators.

poems) were re-constructed in 2022 separately and across different media; specifically, as animated sonnet-shaped text-streams of clustered news titles on monitors and as GPT-2 generated printed sonnets from Twitter posts as prompts.

An exhaustive overview of the changes and their implications exceeds the scope of our current considerations. Nevertheless, the theoretical model referencing the three parameters proves to be valid and useful for preservation efforts, as it offers a systematic approach to delineating the main functions and constituent parts of a new media art project, thus enabling the observation of these as they change in later reconstructions and depending on the contemporary technological environment and societal uses. Furthermore, as a basic model, it can provide an epistemic framework for very different new media artworks and allow for comparisons at an abstracted level.

Concluding remarks: new media art as a tool for understanding the impact of digital technologies on societies

In this paper, we have examined two pilot reconstructions of new media artworks that were nonfunctional in 2022: *Nation – Culture* by Vuk Ćosić and *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club* by Srečo Dragan. In the case of *Nation – Culture*, the online data stream on which the project was based no longer existed at the time of our project. For *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club*, the software could not be accessed on newer systems, and the use of old technology was not infrastructurally viable. In both instances, a simple replacement of parts was insufficient; instead, the reconstruction required a deeper, conceptual understanding of the projects in their contemporary context and in relation to their original communicative function. The artists of the original works chose to build upon the concepts behind the first versions of their work and to reevaluate how it could be integrated into the context of techno-society in 2022, i.e. using new neural network technologies, new data streams, and new communication platforms.

Both pilot projects were selected when the worldwide pandemic recommendations urged social distancing. The *Matrix Coincidence Dating Club* techno-performance takes a step in the opposite direction as it brings people together. Vuk Ćosić's project addresses the negative aspects of the disruption; specifically, the prevalence of online hate speech. Aside from the enforced isolation, the rise of teleconferencing emerged during this period, alongside the parallel exacerbation of echo chambers and filter bubbles within social networks. In 2023, following the two pilot projects, the provision of chat models by most major platforms and online services from hardware and software companies became a reality. In other words, an articulate computer became inconspicuous, with currently unforeseeable consequences. In this context, our approach to born-digital cultural heritage contributes

an important record of how society is evolving in Luciano Floridi's perspective on the fourth revolution and the fourth decentralization of humanity following Copernicus, Darwin, Freud/cognitive science, and Turing. Our previous role as the sole agents in the infosphere must now be reconsidered, taking into account artificial and hybrid agents (Floridi 2014, 87ff). Floridi's project of the *Principia Philosophiae Informationis* and the endeavour to reconceptualize reality in informational terms can be bolstered by preserving historical records of the transition from the predigital to the postdigital age.

A particular quality of new media art is that it highlights the reality of technology; it is not merely a metaphor but a transformative element in our culture, one that carries profound consequences (cf. Castells). A secondary, and unwelcome, outcome of the two pilot studies was the evidence of an ongoing resistance in society to take digital information technologies seriously. One might expect that a political programme aimed at digitising education, health services, and administrative procedures would acknowledge the value of new media art as an open space for experimenting with media literacy and critical thought, both of which accompany artistic practice/art preservation (Lovink 2002). However, this is rarely the case. The two pilot reconstructions clearly demonstrate that, even when one critiques certain technological platforms and their social uses (Ćosić critically focused on Twitter), the intense attention to detail and the reflection on what is actually occurring (e.g. how new neural networks-based projects function, what they actually do), is at the very heart of new media art. And it should be preserved, or at the very least, accounted for in the preservation of such artworks. This could be the key positive insight supported by our project so far.

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